

How «FAIR» is the education data in Switzerland?

An assessment of the status quo

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Abstract

This paper assesses the current state of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles in the context of education data in Switzerland. Based on findings from the SNSF project «Virtual Educational Observatory» (VEO) conducted at the Swiss Institute of Information Science, the paper evaluates how well education datasets¹ adhere to the FAIR principles, which are crucial for effective education monitoring and research.

Despite the increasing digitization in the education sector, there are still many datasets that are either inaccessible or not sufficiently documented for education needs, limiting their usability for researchers. The paper highlights the need for comprehensive metadata and standardized protocols to improve data interoperability and reuse.

The paper concludes with recommendations for enhancing the «FAIRness» of education data in Switzerland, emphasizing the importance of persistent identifiers, detailed and generous metadata, and the use of community standards. These improvements are vital for maximizing the potential of education data to inform policy and practice, ensuring it can be efficiently and effectively utilized by researchers and other stakeholders in the education sector.

¹ See Appendix: 1. *Glossary* for a clarification, how the different terms regarding data, dataset, metadata and so on, are used in this paper.

Motivation

The following report is based on the findings on data findability, data access and data linking options in Swiss education, which were developed in the course of the SNSF project «Virtual Educational Observatory» (VEO). The project, conducted at Swiss Institute for Information Science (SII) at the University of Applied Sciences of the Grisons (FH Graubünden) within the Computational Social and Educational Sciences (CSES) team, is investigating approaches as to how existing or future datasets from the Swiss education sector should be presented and processed so that they can be examined and used as an integrated framework to generate knowledge for education monitoring and education research.

The main task of the project is to demonstrate the potential of data linkages in answering educational questions in Switzerland. However, to be able to link data with each other in a meaningful way, it must first be possible to find this data in its raw form, and it must be accessible. Due to the ever-increasing spread of digitalization in the education sector², the research team initially hoped to be able to draw on a rich pool of digital raw data. However, disillusionment soon set in.

On the one hand, many datasets that are generated as part of the activities of education institutions (schools, cantonal education offices, education research institutes) are only made public and searchable to a limited extent. Many analyses are only carried out internally. And data that is openly accessible is often found in aggregated form and/or has been anonymized to such an extent that it is no longer possible to carry out interesting data linkage and/or data analyses.

In addition, access to datasets with great potential for new findings through linkages is often only possible as part of a specific research project, and the application processes are often complex and lengthy.

Based on the FAIR principles, this paper therefore attempts to take stock of the «FAIRness» of education data in Switzerland to analyse in detail how pronounced the above-mentioned problems are.

Introduction

The FAIR principles (GO FAIR, 2022) state that databases should be easy to find (**F**indability), transparently accessible (**A**ccessibility), inter-linkable (**I**nteroperability) and widely reusable (**R**eusability).

There are several reasons why the implementation of these principles is particularly challenging in the education sector:

- Data from the education sector often contains sensitive information: To be able to make statements at the level of pupils and teachers, the data is often collected in detail and comprehensively. Although there are many technical options for protecting and/or obscuring data at an individual level (data encryption, anonymization/pseudonymization, privacy preserving, authentication) when storing, analysing and providing sensitive data, the implementation of such measures always requires additional time, as well as personnel and

²See also the guidelines on the Federal Council's «Digital Switzerland» strategy (Swiss Confederation (2024) (<https://digital.swiss/de/strategie/strategie.html>) and the EDK's digitalization work plan (<https://www.cdpe.ch/de/themen/transversal/digitalisierung>) (Swiss Conference of Cantonal Ministers of Education (EDK) (2023)

financial resources on the part of the data producers. In addition, data consumers can often only access this sensitive data by submitting a complex data access request.³

- Data is generated in various usage contexts: Data from education researchers and education monitoring, data on the administrative activities of education institutions/municipalities/cantons and the federal government, statistics on the distribution of teaching and learning staff, data from competence measurements/tests/examinations for the purpose of assessing education measures, research data, usage data for teaching and learning materials. Much of this data is available in different formats and data sources. The federal nature of the Swiss education landscape makes it difficult to ensure standardization regarding data formats and data instruments. Although individual harmonizations are underway at both cantonal and federal level⁴, overarching coordination and integration of these diverse data contexts remains a major challenge not only in the education sector.
- Varying quality of data documentation: The diversity of data producers means that different applications and standards are used to store and document the data⁵. One consequence of this is that the quality and detail of the metadata describing the datasets varies greatly. The heterogeneity of the information makes it difficult to use the metadata to estimate in advance which types of data can/may be found and to what extent.

This is just an initial list of the key challenges.

In the following chapters, the topic of «FAIR» data in the Swiss education sector is explored in greater depth, with this paper focusing in particular on the perspective of researchers who are interested in research data in the education sector. The following questions are addressed:

- Why is «FAIR» data so important in education?
- How «FAIR» is data in the Swiss education sector from the researchers' perspective?
- What developments are needed to make education data even more «FAIR»?

Why FAIR data in education?

Data is the central raw material in scientific research, political and economic practice. It is the basis for analyses, decisions, management and control mechanisms.

Regarding the education sector, various stakeholders rely on data to answer the following questions (see also: (educa, 2019), page 25 ff.):

- Confederation and cantons:
 - Do education institutions (schools, universities) have sufficient resources (money, staff, knowledge, skills) to offer teachers/learners the best possible education?
 - Do the education standards and objectives meet the requirements of modern society and the labour market?

³ In a use case for the VEO project, an attempt was made to obtain various datasets on the topic of educational aspiration in Switzerland by means of a data request to be able to link them afterwards. The process of applying for data took several months, partly because new details on the scope and use of the data was repetitively required, but also because the asynchronous communication prevented direct feedback/requests. In addition, it was difficult for the project team to estimate which data attributes would be relevant when linking the data later. Subsequent requests for new data/data attributes would have delayed the whole process even further.

⁴ <https://www.sdbb.ch/datenmanagement/haka> (Schweiz. Dienstleistungszentrum für Berufsbildung (SDBB) (2022) <https://www.bfs.admin.ch/bfs/de/home/nadb/nadb.html> (Federal Statistical Office (2024)

⁵ See also the report «Befragung kantonale Ämter zu Daten in der Bildung» (Schiller et al. (2023)

- Do education legislation and policy take account of the needs of education stakeholders?
- Cantonal Education offices:
 - Can we ensure that curriculum development is in line with current pedagogical knowledge and meets the needs of learners?
 - How can we measure quality in schools and education institutions to maintain high standards of education quality?
 - Are the evaluation mechanisms used to measure the performance of schools and education institutions and promote continuous improvement accurate and valid?
- Education institutions as schools, universities:
 - How satisfied are the students with the educational offerings?
 - What measures can the university take to attract more students?
- Education researchers:
 - How effective is a particular teaching and learning method in promoting more evidence-based pedagogical practices?
 - What are the trends and challenges in the education system?
 - What influence do social, economic and cultural factors have on education outcomes and education equality?
- Education market:
 - How does the use of digital learning platforms and technologies influence learning outcomes and learner engagement?
 - How can predictive analytics help to identify risks of dropping out of education at an early stage and develop appropriate support measures to improve student success?

These are just a few of the many possible questions that education data is invaluable for answering. However, this requires not only a broad, high-quality database, but also the accessibility and availability of this data. Above all, data must be able to be used efficiently and effectively to fully exploit the potential of possible statements.

In recent years, various initiatives and measures have been undertaken in the direction of more open databases and multiple use of data, which also have points of contact with education:

- The National Open Access Strategy developed by swissuniversities and the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF), which aims to ensure the long-term sustainability and development of Open Access in Switzerland (swissuniversities & Swiss National Science Foundation [SNSF], 2024).⁶
- The National Strategy for Open Research Data led by swissuniversities, which aims to promote open access to research data in a coordinated manner in collaboration with the SNSF, the Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI), the two Federal Institutes of Technology and the Swiss Academies of Arts and Sciences (swissuniversities, 2021).⁷
- The Open Government Data Strategy adopted by the Federal Council, which aims to support and anchor open and freely usable administrative data (Open Government Data, 2021).⁸
- The motion initiated by the Federal Office of Justice, which instructs the Federal Council to draw up a basis for a framework law on the secondary use of data (SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND CULTURE COMMITTEES SECC, 2022).⁹

⁶ <https://www.swissuniversities.ch/themen/digitalisierung/open-access/nationale-strategie-und-aktionsplan>

⁷ <https://www.sbfi.admin.ch/sbfi/de/home/hs/hochschulen/hochschulpolitische-themen/open-science.html>

⁸ <https://www.bfs.admin.ch/bfs/en/home/services/ogd/documentation.assetdetail.16164831.html>

⁹ <https://www.parlament.ch/de/ratsbetrieb/suche-curia-vista/geschaefft?AffairId=20223890>

- The mandate commissioned by the Federal Council to create a trustworthy framework for data spaces. This mandate forms the basis for the Swiss data ecosystem project. The aim is to promote the multiple use of data while upholding fundamental principles such as data conformity (Swiss Confederation Federal Chancellery, 2024).¹⁰
- The new Federal Statistics Ordinance (BStatV) is intended to legally enshrine the multiple use of data, increase the transparency and efficiency of data processing and ensure data protection (Federal Department of Home Affairs FDHA, 2023).¹¹

The strategies initiated, show that, in terms of research requirements, it is no longer enough to collect data at great expense and then use it in data silos for personal use only.¹² The simplest possible subsequent and multiple use of data has several advantages. In addition to the possible resource savings already mentioned (costs, personnel, time), there is further potential (Smith, 2008):

- Data can be reanalysed, interpreted and/or linked to other datasets from other sources. This opens opportunities to gain additional new findings and insights alongside the original results.
- Re-use by a broad scientific community not only stimulates interdisciplinary exchange, but the original data is tested anew for its validity and comprehensibility.
- The original interviewees and examined individuals do not have to be asked again and the additional burden of repeated tests, interviews and surveys can be avoided. Particularly in the education sector, where, as already mentioned, very sensitive information is often involved, this data only must be collected once, and the privacy of the individuals is respected.
- The secondary use of data is in line with the principle of data minimization, as it reduces the need to collect new data by reusing existing data, which in turn can significantly reduce the overall data collection effort.¹³
- There is also an increasing amount of data that is automatically generated during administrative activities during digitalization. Easier use and free or at least transparent access to this data can also reduce the need for expensive data collection. The advantages of this administrative data are that it is often up-to-date and does not incur any additional costs, as it is continuously collected as part of administrative processes anyway.

Nevertheless, it should not go unmentioned that secondary use of the data also involves certain risks ((Smith, 2008); (TRIPATHY, 2013).

- By re-accessing and re-using data, there is a repeated risk that gaps in sensitive information will be exploited despite the security measures installed. The risk of an incident is correspondingly higher the more people have access to the data.
- Declarations of consent are usually only valid for the original intended use. In the case of secondary use, these consents would have to be obtained and agreed again. But this is not always done consistently for reasons of cost and time.
- Data is created within a context. This context is still given when the data is originally used by the researcher who produced the data themselves. However, if the data is viewed retrospectively, it may be difficult for external researchers to fully understand this context and

¹⁰ https://www.bk.admin.ch/bk/en/home/digitale-transformation-ikt-lenkung/datenoesystem_schweiz.html

¹¹ https://www.fedlex.admin.ch/filestore/fedlex.data.admin.ch/eli/dl/proj/2023/43/cons_1/doc_5/de/pdf-a/fedlex-data-admin-ch-eli-dl-proj-2023-43-cons_1-doc_5-de-pdf-a.pdf

¹² However, the fact that the secondary use of data is not a new idea is shown by the publications of Glaser, among others, who emphasized the importance of secondary data analysis as early as the beginning of the 1960s and demonstrated its potential for solving challenges in connection with economic efficiency, the willingness of the persons studied to be examined/interviewed again, reassessment of research results and testing the robustness of the variables collected. (Glaser, 1962) .

¹³ <https://dsgvo-gesetz.de/art-5-dsgvo/>

take it into account in the analysis, depending on the scope of the data documentation. This can lead to interpretations and results that may be correct based on the data but could be misinterpreted in terms of context.

Still, it is often not always necessary to fully open the access for the reuse of data. Particularly in the education sector, with its large number of sensitive datasets, this does not make sense and is not always feasible.

On the one hand, there are ways of using remote access and safe labs to manage access to the data in such a way that a certain degree of data protection can be guaranteed despite its high sensitivity, so that researchers can still work with this data at a manageable cost.

On the other hand, and this paper will focus on this in particular, «FAIR» and comprehensively documented metadata is the central element for such sensitive datasets in order to provide data consumers with sufficient information in advance (before a possible request for access to the data) as to whether this dataset is suitable for their use case. «FAIR» metadata, which provides a deeper insight into the nature and scope of the data, can therefore save or at least simplify lengthy clarifications.

Mons et al. have also shown in their paper «Cloudy, increasingly FAIR» that «FAIR» can also be implemented in different gradations (see Illustration 1 on the next page). It must at least be possible to find the data in a first stage. Above all, this requires persistent identifiers that refer to the data. Although open access to the data or even linking the data is desirable, it is not always applicable, and it is depending on the context. As an interim solution, it would be desirable if at least the metadata were made available in a fully transparent and comprehensive manner, and that data access is regulated in such a way that a researcher can at least obtain detailed information on how to apply for access and what clarifications are necessary to do so (Mons et al., 2017).

Data as increasingly FAIR Digital Objects

Illustration 1: Varying degrees of «FAIRness» (Mons et al., 2017, p. 53)

There are also advantages for the data producers themselves. Systematic, comprehensive collection of metadata is time-consuming and labour-intensive, but saves resources overall in the long term (FutureLearn, 2013). Here are a few examples:

- By identifying and displaying similar datasets, duplication can be avoided, and the analysis potential of the original data can be increased.
- By providing detailed documentation of the methodological approach, the scientific community can follow the development of the data, identify qualitative weaknesses and provide valuable feedback, possibly while the project is still running.
- Trust is a key aspect of the secondary use of data. If the processes and protocols for data use are clearly documented and accessible, data users and data subjects can be more confident that their data is being used responsibly and securely.
- A clear and comprehensible declaration of use simplifies subsequent publication and reuse and can lead to new results or even research collaborations.

In 2019, a study by the European Commission concluded that the consistent application of the FAIR principles could save up to 10 billion euros in Europe alone. Data is often stored multiple times in different locations, which leads to increased costs as additional storage space is required. Inefficient management and/or non-transparent access to data also leads to increased workloads for both data producers and data consumers. Another cost factor is that there is a risk of researchers conducting the same studies or experiments multiple times because they do not know that the data already exists. Furthermore, if data is not easily accessible, researchers and institutions must apply for it in sometimes lengthy processes. All this leads to considerable additional costs, which could be reduced, at least to a certain extent, by consistently applying the FAIR principles (European Commission. Directorate General for Research and Innovation. & PwC EU Services., 2018).

But it should also be noted that the «FAIR» principles and their application per se are not a remedy for poor quality data. They do not claim to replace a comprehensive, clean data management plan, nor can they do so. Nevertheless, the «FAIR» principles show ways in which data can be described as soon as it is created and stored in such a way that it remains interesting, usable and, above all, interpretable for possible subsequent use in addition to its initial intended purpose.

How FAIR is data in the Swiss education sector?

To be able to assess how «FAIR» data on Swiss education is, the first step is to have an overview of which data sources are available. As already mentioned, education data is generated in various contexts of use (see also educa, 2019, p. 13ff.):

- Schools, universities of applied sciences, universities of teacher education and universities generate administrative (administration, registration) and performance-related data (grades, tests, certificates) on their pupils/students, but also on lecturers, teaching staff and employees.
- Many of the higher education institutes conduct education research themselves to record and analyse education concepts and methods, and regularly publish studies, reports and reports based on this data, some of which are made available in publicly accessible repositories.
- On behalf of the federal government, cantonal education offices collect statistical data from schools, which they submit to the Federal Statistical Office once a year. In addition, some of these offices also conduct their own surveys on education (Schiller et al., 2023).
- Institutionalized national (PISA, ÜGK, TREE) and cantonal studies on education regularly collect performance, contextual and subjective data to record the status and attitudes of pupils and to be able to follow their development in detail.
- Education institutions and, above all, private sector providers such as publishers of teaching materials, operators of online platforms and other service providers use their applications to generate data on the use of their products, social media and other digital media.

All this data is stored internally in various repositories and databases, but some of it is also made available via publicly accessible repositories and data portals.

The diversity of data sources makes it difficult to assess the «FAIRness» of this data in general:

- The federal structure of Switzerland with its cantonal differences is reflected in the data storage used, the quality of data documentation and the transparency of data access. Some cantonal offices still store their data in Excel files and only provide further, additional information on their data on request, while other, larger institutions store the data in searchable databases and repositories (Schiller et al., 2023).
- In addition, it makes a big difference in terms of findability, access and reuse of the data whether it was collected for the purpose of later dissemination or whether it was generated automatically as part of administrative activities.
- Datasets deriving of software applications from the private sector (like log files and user data), which are only intended for internal purposes, cannot be assessed regarding their «FAIRness» simply because the metadata, let alone the data itself, is not publicly accessible.

Nevertheless, the following pages will attempt to assess the «FAIRness» of the found data sources on Swiss education based on the FAIR principles.

Methodology of the assessment

The individual data sources and repositories containing relevant datasets on the topic of education were searched individually by the author for their metadata. If the data source/repository contained many datasets, only individual samples were taken on the assumption that the metadata would be assigned consistently across all datasets. The metadata found were assessed according to the FAIR recommendations and the key results for each individual FAIR criterion were recorded in a table. The corresponding tables 1-4 can be found in the Appendix: 3. *Overview of FAIR Assessment education data sources in Switzerland*).

To make it easier to understand what the individual FAIR principles mean in concrete terms, all principles are first explained in detail with special attention to the needs of education researchers. This is then followed by of an assessment of the status quo of the «FAIRness» for each type of data source.

Findable

Explanations of the four principles F1-F4 for the retrievability of education records

To be able to analyse the rich treasure trove of education data, it must first be possible to find it. According to the FAIR principles, a description of a dataset should contain at least the following attributes so that the dataset is and, above all, remains findable for data consumers (FORCE11, 2021); GO FAIR, 2022):

F1 Persistent Identifiers (PID) - Unique and persistent identifiers for the dataset that remain stable over time.

- Examples of such persistent identifiers are the DOI (Digital Object Identifier) or the URN (Uniform Resource Name). To use a PID, the digital object (in this case the dataset) must be registered with a PID registration authority (for a DOI, for example, this would be the DataCite consortium¹⁴). PIDs can be resolved via specialized resolver services, which then provide the current storage location of the object.¹⁵ The great advantage of a PID is that the data record always has the same «address» under which it can be found, even if the storage location of the data record is moved.
 - PID can also be used by both humans and machines, so applications can, for example, always use the same DOI to automatically retrieve the resource and integrate it into their analyses. The machine uses the resolver service to find and access the current location of the resource.
 - In contrast to PIDs, normal URLs, such as those used for Internet addresses, are not persistent per se, as they can change if, for example, the website on which the data record is stored is reorganized or moved to another server.
 - The education sector benefits in particular from such persistent identifiers, as the large number of data producers, data sources and data objects means that resources often become orphaned and can no longer be found after a certain period of time.
- *F2 Rich metadata - Comprehensive and generous description of the dataset that enables the content, context and use of the dataset to be understood.*¹⁶

¹⁴ <https://datacite.org/>

¹⁵ For example, if you enter the identification number (10.nnnnnn/example) for a DOI in the resolver at <https://www.doi.org/>, you will always be taken to the corresponding resource.

¹⁶ As an illustrative example, a fictitious example data record is shown in the Appendix: 2. *Fictitious educational example data record*, where based on the learnings an attempt was made to create a metadataset for education in accordance with the FAIR principles and the findings presented here, which would satisfy all criteria as optimally as possible.

- The meaning of the words «extensive» and «generous» is a matter of interpretation. However, the principle behind them is that you should not skimp on descriptions. You never know in advance what information might be of interest to a researcher and what details they might be looking for. As an absolute minimum, at least the core elements of a dataset should be described. What this absolute minimum should be in order to make a dataset easier to find is not explicitly mentioned in the FAIR principles. The specification of the «FAIRsFAIR - Fostering Fair Data Practices in Europe» project group (Devaraju et al., 2020) has defined the following minimum metadata for findability based on common data citation guidelines and metadata recommendations.
 - Title of the data record
 - Creator
 - Identifier
 - Abstract/Description/Summary
 - Publication date
 - Publisher
 - Keywords
- This metadata should also be readable and interpretable for both humans and machines.
- In the field of education, however, other elements could also be relevant for researchers, such as¹⁷:
 - Type of population (pupils, teachers, school staff, etc.)
 - Type of survey method (test, surveys, interviews, etc.)
 - Information on the sample (education level, age, school type)
 - Geographical coverage (which cantons were examined?)
 - Data collection period
- Researchers often use such education-specific information to search for potentially interesting datasets. The search for these elements should be implemented both via the search interface and via possible filters, so that the hits found can be further specified according to these criteria.
- *F3 Link/PID to the data record itself - A direct link or reference that enables access to the data record.*
 - The persistent link should be listed in the metadata itself. The link allows the dataset to be clearly identified and processed by humans and machines. Metadata with an explicit link (PID) provides a clear and unambiguous link to the data. This link is crucial for the interoperability and reusability of the data.
 - An explicit link in the metadata also ensures that the data can be traced and retrieved correctly in the future, even if the physical structure or storage location of the data changes.
 - For the education sector, the inclusion of identifiers in the metadata not only improves the findability and operability of education resources by humans and machines, it also enables education researchers and technical systems to reference the sources more easily and cite them more consistently.
- *F4 Indexed in a searchable database: The data record should be recorded in a database that makes it possible to find the data record using search functions.*

¹⁷ See Peralta et al. (2018) or Simao de Deus and Francine Barbosa (2020) for a discussion of the challenges encountered when deciding what metadata is required for educational resources.

- Using a search function is the first step in a researcher's search. Searching for the data record using keywords, free text and filtering options increases and facilitates the findability of the data record enormously.
- When records are indexed in a database, search engines and database applications can also search the data quickly and find and retrieve relevant information more easily. In addition, an index increases the efficiency of search systems by allowing them to access an organized list of keywords or attributes instead of having to search through the entire data each time. This means that queries are answered more quickly.
- The FAIR principle does not explicitly state that the database must be accessible online. Nevertheless, online access makes it easier to find the dataset. Nowadays, most researchers search for relevant datasets via the Internet. If a dataset is stored in an online searchable, indexed database, this greatly increases the chance that it will be found.
- It would also be helpful if the database could at least be found via a Google search in the top ranks. With the large number of repositories, it is becoming increasingly difficult and time-consuming to find all the data sources that would be/are relevant.
- It would also be advantageous if data records were stored in established databases that are regularly used by the respective community. The users of this community know where to search and are familiar with the search tools and the structure of the database. In addition, storing datasets in community-appropriate databases facilitates data exchange and integration with other research results and projects within the community. In addition, databases that are well established in the community often enjoy a high level of trust and acceptance. Datasets stored in such databases are more likely to be considered reliable and of high quality. Plus, specialized, established databases usually have implemented mechanisms for quality assurance and peer review, which can further increase the quality and trustworthiness of the submitted datasets.

The four principles of discoverability ensure that datasets are and remain useful and accessible not only for current but also for future generations by laying the foundation for the long-term storage, search and reuse of data.

Status quo for finding data sources on education in Switzerland

The data sources that contain relevant data on education in Switzerland can be roughly divided into the following four categories (see Tables 1-4):

- International repositories such as Zenodo, Figshare, Data Dryad, Open Science Framework (OSF)
- National repositories & data sources such as SWISSUbase, Federal Statistical Office, opendata.swiss
- Institutional repositories of universities, universities of applied sciences and universities of teacher education (if available)
- Data portals of the cantonal statistical offices

With the exception of opendata.swiss, none of these repositories/data sources is a pure research data repository, but mainly contains studies, reports and statistics, which are occasionally accompanied by individual datasets.

The international and national repositories are generally sufficiently «FAIR» in terms of the findability of the datasets. *Persistent indicators (F1)* are available in most cases¹⁸, *a link to the dataset (F3)* is

¹⁸ The Federal Statistical Office must be somewhat excluded from this. It only makes aggregated datasets available to the public and is a special case in the sense that it was not created to search for individual datasets,

always provided, except for Figshare, and the dataset can be found using a simple search query (F4). As far as the *rich description of the datasets* (F2) is concerned, the information is according to the FAIR principles at least sufficient to find the datasets - for the information that is central to the findability of a dataset in every research discipline, such as...

... Title and originator of the data record

... Publisher of the data record

... Identifier of the data record

... Date of data collection and publication

... Relevant keywords

... Data description

...these repositories perform well.¹⁹

However, it should be discussed if the core metadata is sufficient for finding dataset based on specific education research needs. Sure, the FAIR principles R1.3 (see page 20) addresses community relevant metadata, but there it is more about the reusability of the data, while here it is about the findability. It might be important for researchers to be able to search the dataset for further domain-specific terms to find the specific dataset, especially in the field of education with its different questions:

- Description of the sample (e.g. gender, age group, level of education)
- Geographical coverage of the study (e.g. canton)
- Subject area or specific education field (e.g. mathematics, languages, natural sciences)
- Description of the curriculum or education standards considered in the data
- Context of the learning environment (e.g. traditional classroom, online learning, blended learning)
- Type of education institution (e.g. public school, private school, university)
- Information on whether the data is longitudinal or cross-sectional plus the period and frequency of data collection for longitudinal studies

Although there are a few repositories that offer such metadata relevant to the education sector - for example, SWISSUbase or Data Dryad occasionally provide information on sampling or education level - in most cases this additional education-relevant information is missing, is not consistently supplied with every dataset or is mentioned within a descriptive text and is therefore not easy to find.

Among the institutional repositories, there are a few universities such as the University of Geneva, Bern, Bern University of Teacher Education and the ETH, which offer a repository with some datasets, and these repositories at least meet the four FAIR principles in terms of findability, but there is hardly any data on education topics to be found in them. None of the other institutions have education data

but for statistics. For this reason, a PID is missing for the data record in question (an internal identifier is however available).

¹⁹ At the Federal Statistical Office, some of the metadata can be found in the description of the data, while detailed metadata on how the data was obtained is somewhat hidden in the footnotes of the interactive tables (data cubes). This separation makes it cumbersome for researchers to find all the information on the data.

in their repositories²⁰, not to mention specific data repositories (regarding the reasons why Universities of Teacher Education have no data repositories – mostly due to limited resources – see also the report by Schiller et al., 2024). However, some universities (e.g. Lucerne), universities of applied sciences (e.g. HES-SO) and universities of teacher education (e.g. PH St. Gallen) provide their data to external repositories such as Zenodo, OSF and SWISSUbase.

The data from the cantonal education offices is in turn processed by the relevant statistical office and published on their websites. Many cantons publish statistics on learners, teachers and other education stakeholders on their online portals. However, the underlying data cannot usually be searched efficiently due to a lack of search options or insufficient information (see also the report Schiller et al., 2023). At least there are some cantons, such as Aargau, Bern, Basel Stadt, Fribourg and Schwyz, which provide more extensive metadata that can help you search for data. There are also a few cantonal statistics portals on which the datasets are not described individually, but only summarized on an overview page. As a result, the individual datasets lack their own metadata and persistent identifiers, which makes it difficult or even impossible to reference these data unambiguously.

Accessible

Explanations of the four principles A1, A1.1, A1.2 & 2 on the accessibility of education datasets

In the context of FAIR Data, accessibility does not mean the disclosure of all research data (open data). According to the FAIR principles, data may well be hidden behind an access restriction, and this makes sense for sensitive data. But at least the metadata should always be accessible and for an indefinite period, preferably online and technically implemented in such a way that not only humans but also machines can retrieve it automatically without any problems. It is also important to provide precise information in the metadata about the conditions under which the data can be accessed by both humans and machines. The following three FAIR principles address these aspects (FORCE11, 2021; GO FAIR, 2022):

- *A1 & A1.1 (Meta)-data is made accessible through standardized, open and universally implementable access protocols.*²¹
 - Standardized, widely used communication protocols such as HTTP/HTTPS make it possible for data to be accessed consistently across different platforms and systems from any client/browser. An additional API also offers the option of automated access to the data.
 - The use of universally implementable protocols facilitates global and barrier-free access to data by ensuring that data is accessible regardless of geographical location, technological infrastructure and end-user needs.
 - A universal implementation also promotes interoperability between different systems and platforms, which facilitates the reuse and integration of data.
 - In the education sector, where data from different institutions can be available in different formats and types, standardized, universally implementable protocols make it much easier to access and use the (meta)-data. These protocols ensure broad accessibility of (meta)-data for all types of education institutions, researchers and systems, thus making it easier for people and machines to exchange information with each other.
 - In the case of sensitive data, it should at least be possible to retrieve the metadata via an open, standardized and universally implementable communication protocol.

²⁰ ZORA (<https://www.zora.uzh.ch/>) at the University of Zurich has some resources on education, but no explicit education datasets.

²¹ Principles A1 and A1.1 are for practical reasons summarized here, as both address the communication protocols via which the (meta)-data can be retrieved.

- *A1.2 The protocols offer authentication and authorization options.*
 - Authentication ensures that the identity of the user/machine is verified before access is granted to the sometimes very sensitive data. This can be done using various methods (e.g. username/password, HTTPS²² , OAuth²³), which help to ensure the security of the data by only granting access to authorized users.
 - Authorization, in turn, ensures that users can only view or manipulate the data for which they have the appropriate rights. This is often controlled by role or rights assignments. Authorization is important for implementing access controls that regulate access to sensitive or confidential data.
 - The need for authentication and authorization depends on the context and sensitivity of the data. Public data often does not require authentication, while sensitive or personal data requires stricter access controls.
 - In the education sector, with its large number of sensitive data records, it is essential that authentication and access control is possible via protocols. In this way, access can be guaranteed selectively, and the data can be made accessible in a controlled manner despite its high sensitivity.
- *A2 The metadata is accessible even if the dataset itself is no longer accessible.*
 - Metadata should be stored in such a way that it remains accessible in the long term, even if the actual data records are deleted, moved or no longer available for other reasons. Metadata contains important information about the data, how it was collected and processed.
 - To ensure that metadata remains accessible even if the data is no longer available, the following measures can be taken:
 - Storage of data in long-lasting repositories: Interdisciplinary repositories supported and fed in by a broad community offer a certain degree of security that the data will remain accessible for a long time due to their broad user base and available resources.
 - Use of persistent identifiers: DOIs or other persistent identifiers ensure that metadata is registered (e.g. in DataCite²⁴) and can be permanently referenced.
 - Regular backups and archiving: Backup strategies and archiving ensure that metadata is not lost and can be restored even in the event of technical failures.
 - Open and standardized metadata formats: Use of metadata standards for metadata description such as Dublin Core, Schema.org or, for the education sector, Learning Resource Metadata Initiative (LRMI) to ensure long-term interoperability and accessibility.
 - Thanks to these measures, researchers and other users can continue to access the metadata years later to understand what data existed and how it was used, even if they can no longer retrieve the data themselves.
 - Other researchers can use the metadata to reproduce or continue studies or create new datasets based on the methods and contexts described.
 - Unfortunately, the long-term availability of datasets is not always guaranteed in the education sector with its large number of different datasets. It is therefore even more important to provide clearly documented metadata beyond the intended use to make the traceability and contexts of origin of the datasets comprehensible and transparent for education researchers.

²² <https://www.rfc-editor.org/rfc/rfc9110.html>

²³ <https://oauth.net/2/>

²⁴ <https://datacite.org/>

Status quo on the accessibility of data sources on education in Switzerland

Regarding FAIR principles *A1, A1.1 and A1.2 - standardized, open protocols that offer authorization/authentication options* - all those repositories and data sources that are freely accessible online via the Internet meet these principles.

All international and national repositories fulfil this requirement.

Access to the universities is not always available for this reason alone, as the majority of them do not yet have a repository with datasets. Among those that do make exciting datasets available, there are two universities (École Poly-technique Fédérale de Lausanne EPFL and University of Basel) where access is only open to members. The other institutional repositories (BORIS, yareta.ch, OLOS, ETH Research Collection, REPO PH Bern) fulfil all three principles.

At least two thirds of the cantonal statistics offices have an online portal with datasets and statistics that are freely accessible on the internet. The cantons of Appenzell Ausserrhoden, Glarus, Graubünden, Nid- and Obwalden, Solothurn, Uri and Valais do not offer their own data on their websites but refer to the Federal Statistical Office or to data portals of other cantons.

Regarding FAIR Principle *A2 - metadata are available even if the datasets themselves are no longer accessible* - there is potential for improvement, particularly at the cantonal statistics offices.

Most of the offices only make their datasets available via URL. Some also do not have their own metadata entries but provide the datasets on a website summarized in a list form. In addition to the fact that specific metadata cannot be provided, it is questionable whether this metadata will still be available if the URL is changed, or the dataset is deleted.

In the case of the national data sources from the Federal Statistical Office and opendata.swiss, the datasets have internal identifiers, but it is difficult to assess whether the metadata would still be accessible via the current URL if the storage location of the data were to change.

SWISSUbase, all international and institutional repositories that make data available, all use a persistent DOI to identify their (meta)-data and the metadata are registered in a global directory (r3data.org²⁵), which ensures access to them even if the dataset is no longer available.

Interoperable

Explanations of the three principles I1-I3 for the interoperability of education datasets

In the context of the FAIR principles, interoperability means that data and metadata are structured and described in such a way that they can be seamlessly communicated and processed between different systems, platforms and applications. This is particularly important for education data to be able to link datasets and applications from different education institutions, learning platforms and administrative systems and thus facilitate the exchange of information. The following three FAIR principles address interoperability (FORCE11, 2021; GO FAIR, 2022):

- *I1 Formal, widely used and versatile representation language that is also accessible to machines.*
 - A representation language is a formal system for describing data or knowledge that follows specific syntactic and semantic rules. These rules are used to represent information in a structured, precise and understandable way that is accessible to both humans and machines. In the context of the FAIR principles, and particularly the interoperability principle I1, this means that the data and metadata are described in a way

²⁵ <https://www.re3data.org/>

that enables efficient processing and interpretation by different software and hardware systems.

- A formal representation language is based on well-defined syntax and semantic rules. These rules ensure that the language can be read, interpreted and processed precisely and unambiguously. The clear structure and rules ensure that fewer misunderstandings arise during interpretation by humans and machines, thereby facilitating the exchange of information.
- The language used should be widely accepted and usable in different application areas to promote interoperability. The advantage is wider acceptance and compatibility with a variety of systems and tools.
- Examples of such representation languages are RDF, XML, JSON LD, OWL. Metadata standards such as DDI or Dublin Core fulfil this principle, as they are based on an XML or JSON structure.
- Ideally, data repositories also provide an application programming interface (API) to enable easier automated access to data from different systems, domains and disciplines.²⁶
- In terms of education data, the principle ensures that education researchers can not only combine and analyse data from different sources, but also create learning environments and applications that can import and integrate this data from different systems.
- *I2 (Meta)-data use vocabularies which themselves follow the FAIR principles.*²⁷
 - In terms of education data, this principle means that the vocabulary used to describe the data should also be findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable.
 - In concrete terms, this means that the controlled vocabularies used to describe the data should be comprehensively documented, but the documentation should also be easy to find and access, referenced and resolvable using a persistent, global identifier and described using a common representation language.
 - In education, the principle ensures that the vocabularies used to describe and classify education data themselves comply with the FAIR principles. This promotes higher quality, interoperability and reusability of data, which ultimately contributes to a more efficient and effective education ecosystem. For example, by using standardized and FAIR-compliant vocabularies, education systems can seamlessly exchange data with each other, or education researchers can use standardized and FAIR-compliant vocabularies to analyse and compare education data more efficiently.
 - Established metadata standards such as Dublin Core, DDI or education-specific LRMI fulfil this FAIR requirement and it is therefore advisable to use these standards for the description of data records. Nevertheless, you could also create your own descriptions if the vocabulary complies with the FAIR principles.
- *I3 (Meta)-data contain qualified references to other (meta)data.*
 - This means that the data and metadata should explicitly and unambiguously refer to other relevant data or metadatasets. These references contribute to the interoperability and usability of the data by enabling a deeper and interconnected structure of the data landscape.
 - Qualified links are links that not only establish a simple link to other datasets, but also make the context, the type of relationship and/or the meaning of these links explicit. Such

²⁶ Although the topic of API is not explicitly mentioned in the FAIR principle, an API plays an important role regarding the interoperability of systems.

²⁷ Controlled vocabularies are not the same as a representation language. Representational languages define how data is structured and represented. Vocabularies, on the other hand, define the specific terms and concepts within this structure.

references help to understand the data in a larger context and make it possible to easily find, integrate and contextualize other relevant information.

- For the education sector, such explicit references are useful so that education researchers can not only understand the origin and links of datasets more transparently, but also simplify the aggregation of other relevant datasets. Particularly regarding linking new datasets, such cross-references can provide additional information on which datasets can be considered for linking.²⁸ This contributes to a networked data landscape that increases the quality and efficiency of education processes and research, creates synergies and semantically relates data both within and outside the domain.²⁹

Status quo on the interoperability of data sources on education in Switzerland

The FAIR principles *I1 - Formal, machine-accessible, widely used and versatile representation language* - and *I2 - (Meta)-data using vocabularies that themselves follow the FAIR principles* - national, international and - if available - institutional repositories/data sources fulfil this principle. Representation languages are either in XML or JSON, rarely also RDF (Data Dryad). At least all national and international repositories have an API interface in XML, JSON. The ETH Research Collection offers an API interface for institutional data sources. In terms of metadata standards, two thirds of international, national and institutional repositories use Dublin Core or the DataCite Metadata Schema. A few use the DCAT-AP CH (opendata.swiss) or the DDI standard (SWISSUbase). The Federal Statistical Office does not mention any specific metadata standard on which the datasets are based.

The cantonal data portals present a mixed picture in terms of interoperability. Only 4 of the 26 cantons offer an API interface on their portals (cantons of Aargau, Basel Stadt, Fribourg and Schwyz). Regarding metadata standards, a standard could only be determined for the data portals of the cantons of Basel Stadt and Fribourg (DCAT-AP CH).

With FAIR Principle *I3 - (Meta)-data contain qualified references to other (meta)-data* - the status quo looks less good. Among the international repositories, Zenodo and the Open Science Framework occasionally have references to related datasets or additional materials, but these are rarely explicit. With Zenodo, you can at least see an indication of the type of reference, e.g. «is supplement to -> Software». But overall, there is a lack of consistency and semantically adequately described references.

Although the national repositories occasionally have references to associated datasets or higher-level studies (SWISSUbase and the Federal Statistical Office), overall references to other interesting datasets are not consistently given and/or the references are not always meaningful.

The institutional repositories show a similar picture. Yareta.ch, ETH Research Collection and OLOS offer cross-references in some cases, and at least the ETH Research Collection also indicates the type of reference. For education researchers and automated systems, however, it is also very difficult to locate related data records, as the references are only sparsely assigned and only rarely in a qualified manner.

Among the cantonal data portals, only 3 cantons have explicit references to further or related datasets on their websites (Canton Aargau, Basel Stadt, Fribourg). However, the type of relationship is not specified. The cantons of Geneva, St. Gallen, Ticino, Vaud, Zug, and the cities of Bern and Zurich at

²⁸ Although one of the main advantages of data links is that data records that initially have no points of contact can also be linked together.

²⁹ Whereby the topic of "linked data" naturally goes one step further. However, we will not go into this in depth here.

least have further links to additional statistics/data somewhere on the website, but this is not machine-readable, and it is also rather unsuitable for researchers to get a quick overview of relevant, related data.

Reusable

Explanations of the four principles R1, R1.1, R1.2 & R1.3 for the reusability of education datasets

Reusability is another key aspect of the FAIR principles, which aims to ensure that data and metadata are designed and accessed in such a way that they can be reused by other researchers and applications. For education data, reuse is particularly welcome, as the assessment and collection of education data is not only costly, but also, as mentioned above, the sensitivity of the data means that the individuals surveyed/studied should not be unnecessarily burdened by constant re-sampling. The principles of reusability are as follows:

- *R1 Relevant, detailed description of all aspects of a dataset that could be of interest to the respective stakeholders.*
 - In contrast to FAIR Principle F2, this principle focuses on metadata that is particularly relevant for reusability. Metadata on education data should therefore not only contain information that an education researcher would look for, but also details about it that enable the researcher to assess the usefulness of this data regarding reuse.
 - As you can never be sure in advance what the initial data will be used for in the future, you should be generous and provide as much metadata as possible. The metadata should therefore be comprehensive but also precise. This makes it easier for others to find the data, interpret it and use it in their own work.
 - Providing rich metadata ensures that the data can be understood in the right context. This includes not only information about the data collection methods, the purpose of the data collection, the limitations of the data, but also other information such as the meaning of response scales, details on the methods of data cleansing and statistical procedures for data analysis. This principle is also addressed by the fact that the data variables are given self-explanatory names or, even more ideally, that they are explained in detail.
 - When assessing the reuse of datasets, the researcher needs as accurate a picture as possible of how the data was collected, processed and disseminated. This necessity is illustrated by this principle.
 - In the education sector, with its large number of data collections, data analyses and methods, this insight into data generation and further processing is even more important than elsewhere.
- *R1.1 Clear and detailed description of access conditions and rights of use.*
 - The access conditions regulate how the data may be used, passed on and modified. The aim is to avoid legal uncertainties and maximize the reusability of the data by making the conditions for use as transparent as possible.
 - The choice of a suitable license and its comprehensive description enables data producers to define the conditions for the use of their data in an understandable way, which facilitates reuse by others and at the same time ensures legal protection.
 - An accessible and understandable license also encourages others not only to use the data, but also to redistribute it and integrate it into new projects (if this is permitted in the license).
 - Of course, it would be desirable if as much data as possible were made available under open licenses such as Creative Commons (CC) or GNU General Public License (GPL). But as already mentioned, this is not always feasible for sensitive datasets despite

anonymization and pseudonymization, is not always desired, or is not done because too much information would otherwise be lost.

- Education datasets may be made restrictive behind access restrictions. With these datasets, however, it is even more important for the education researcher to be able to assess in advance to what extent admission is permitted, how long and how time-consuming admission will be and what costs are involved.
- For many datasets in education, informed consent is also required from the data providers at the time of collection. This consent is often only valid for the initial purpose of use. The metadata should therefore specify in detail whether datasets are available for secondary use at all and, if so, to what extent and under what conditions.
- *R1.2 (Meta)-data should contain detailed origin information.*
 - Indications of origin or provenance descriptions document the origins, history and development of the data. This includes information about who collected, analysed and published the data, when which methods were used and which data were collected, which changes were made to the dataset and to what extent, and whether there have already been publications relating to the data. Ideally, a workflow should be provided that allows the data to be traced from its origin to its current status.
 - Providing detailed provenance increases trust in the data, as users can understand its origin and the methods used to collect it. Provenance information also enables a better assessment of data quality and makes it easier to identify errors or inconsistencies.
 - Education researchers and teachers can use and reuse the data more efficiently if they understand the exact origin and methods that led to the data collection. Any questions that arise can be clarified in advance or, if necessary, placed with the creator of the data.
 - However, indications of origin also support compliance with ethical and legal guidelines by creating transparency about the source and use of data.
 - In the education sector, data is collected at so many levels that it is almost impossible for education researchers, as well as people involved in education monitoring, to trace the data paths across all origins. Detailed provenance information therefore makes a decisive contribution to providing an overview of the data landscape and increasing the efficiency and effectiveness of data use and reuse.
- *R1.3 (Meta)-data conforms to domain-relevant community standards.*
 - Community standards are norms and guidelines accepted by the community for the collection, presentation and management of data. They are the result of collaborative efforts by experts and institutions within a particular domain. These standards ensure that data is consistent, reliable and of high quality, which facilitates sharing and reuse.
 - Education data should therefore be described in accordance with internationally recognized metadata standards that are established in the respective community and beyond. These standards define what information should be recorded and how it should be structured. The use of such standards increases trust in the data, both among the producers and the users of the data.
 - There are some established metadata standards for the education sector, such as Learning Object Metadata (LOM) for describing learning objects, Learning Resource Metadata Initiative (LRMI) for describing learning resources, but the Dublin Core or DDI metadata standards can also be adapted to the needs of education researchers.
 - However, the principle of using domain-specific standards applies not only to the metadata itself, but also to the data. Standardized data formats and structures facilitate the reuse and efficient use of data in different contexts and domains. Interoperable, widely used and platform-independent data formats such as CSV, JSON and XML support the reusability of data records and should be preferred as a storage format.

- For some domains, there are so-called Minimal Information Standards (MIS).³⁰ These standards specify the minimum basic information required to make data useful and usable in a specific context. However, the MIS also contain specifications on the data formats in which the data records should be available and how they must be described. MIS not only facilitate the reuse of data by other researchers in the respective sector, but also enable the comparison of data from different studies and promote the transparency and reproducibility of scientific research. However, as far as the author is aware, there are unfortunately no MIS for education-related metadata descriptions and data.

Status quo on the reusability of data sources on Swiss education

The aspect of reusability is still given too little consideration in the repositories examined.

Rich metadata is generally supplied too sparsely (*R1*). Although there are, for example, entries on Data Dryad, SWISSUbase, the Federal Statistical Office, yareta.ch, OLOS and on some cantonal data portals (Aargau, Bern, Basel Stadt, Fribourg), there are certainly entries containing additional information that enable education researchers to assess the suitability of the dataset for reuse - there are isolated references to the methodology, sampling, or geographical and temporal details of the survey - but overall, the majority of data sources lack more specific, detailed information on the research design of the studies from which the datasets were created. Particularly in the case of the cantonal data portals, the information is also linked in a separate document and/or hidden in free text and is therefore not prepared in a machine-friendly way.

In the *license information (R1.1)*, at least the datasets of international, national and existing institutional repositories contain information on the type of license - often with a link to further information on the license. However, for those datasets for which access has been made restrictive after a data access clarification, most databases lack important information on the conditions (or are not easy to find per se) under which the data can be requested and how long the data request process takes. Only SWISSUbase provides more detailed information on the data declaration for its restrictive datasets. For the most part, the cantonal statistics portals lack information on the license and/or information on this is hidden on subpages of the website.

No repository provides *detailed information on the origin of its data (R1.2)*. Some databases such as SWISSUbase and the data portals of the cantons of Bern, Basel City, Fribourg and Lucerne have specific information on the methods for some datasets (sometimes hidden in a linked document), which can be used to reconstruct the origin of the data to some extent, but generally there is a lack of a consistent data history with relevant information on data collection, data analysis, data publication and data changes.

Although contact details and information on the versioning of the data are available in almost all repositories (at least the last modification date of the dataset is given almost everywhere), it is not possible to trace the changes to the dataset over time from its original creation to its current status.

The statistical offices often have no version information at all.

Regarding *R1.3 - (meta)data conforming to domain-relevant community standards* - the overall picture is similarly inadequate. Although many of the international, national and institutional repositories use metadata standards such as Dublin Core, DDI, DataCite Metadata Schema, which can also be mapped

³⁰ The term originally comes from biology, where, for example, the Minimum Information About a Microarray Experiment "MIAME" was specified:
[https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/info/MIAME.html#:~:text=The%20MIAME%20\(Minimum%20Information%20About,a%20microarray%20or%20sequencing%20study](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/info/MIAME.html#:~:text=The%20MIAME%20(Minimum%20Information%20About,a%20microarray%20or%20sequencing%20study).

to education content to a certain extent, metadata relevant to education can hardly be found in the descriptions. Most databases have an interdisciplinary structure, and you will only find metadata that can be used to describe as many resources as possible from all disciplines. As a result, there is a lack of more specific information that would enable education researchers to specifically assess the dataset for its reusability.

Regarding data formats, at least the majority, if not all, of international, national and institutional repositories always offer their datasets in software-independent, widely used data formats such as CSV and JSON, which are not only accepted and frequently used in the respective community, but also promote the reusability of datasets across disciplines. Nevertheless, it would be desirable if these open, platform-independent, widely accepted data formats were offered consistently in all data repositories. After all, there are always datasets where the data is only available in Excel format.

Among the cantons, six portals offer their datasets in CSV throughout (Canton Aargau, Basel Stadt, Fribourg, Thurgau, Zurich and Schwyz), while the other cantons only offer the data in Excel (Canton Bern, Basel Landschaft, Lucerne, St. Gallen, Schaffhausen, Ticino, Vaud, Zug and the City of Zurich). It would be desirable if all cantons offered their data at least in CSV.

Recommendations

Overall, the status quo of the «FAIRness» of the metadata of the data sources containing relevant datasets relating to Switzerland is quite sufficient, even if there is room for improvement.

The findability, accessibility, interoperability and reuse of data for education researchers could be further improved if the following measures were implemented consistently across all repositories that make datasets available:

- The respective metadata for the dataset is made available online in a publicly accessible data portal, a website, a repository, and the user can search the dataset in all its metadata using a search interface. Extensive filtering options are also offered. The cantonal data portals in particular lack advanced search functions, but the other repositories could also benefit from more filters relevant to the education sector.
 - At least the metadata should be available in a publicly accessible data portal. This means that it can be viewed by anyone, regardless of institutional access restrictions, and the researcher can decide based on the metadata whether to apply for access.
 - Searchable metadata and extensive filter options enable researchers to find specific datasets quickly and precisely. This reduces the time and effort required to search for relevant data.
 - Researchers can also search for specific criteria, such as sample description, geographical coverage, level of education and methodology. These specific search options improve the relevance of the data records found and considerably enhance and support the research process.
- Globally unique, persistent identifiers are explicitly listed for EACH individual dataset, which can be resolved via URL. Here too, the datasets of the cantonal statistics offices could benefit the most. It should not be the case that datasets without a PID can no longer be found simply because the dataset or website has been moved. The reasons are listed here again for clarification:
 - This means that data records can be retrieved consistently for a longer period. This should also be in the interests of education data producers, as data in the education sector is time-consuming and cost-intensive to collect.

- Explicitly listed PIDs promote interoperability between different databases and systems by providing a standardized method of identification and linking.
- PIDs enable clear and unambiguous citation of datasets in scientific publications, which facilitates traceability and recognition of the data source.
- The datasets are supplemented with the aforementioned additional education-related metadata regarding findability, reuse and access (see also Appendix: 2. *Fictitious education example data record*). This applies to all repositories examined. Education datasets should be described and labelled according to the needs of education researchers, because why create such datasets if not for the future main users? And for them, the dataset should be as easy to find and effective to use as possible.
 - Education researchers also search and evaluate the datasets according to education-specific information such as education levels, school types, class sizes, etc. The more search entries and the more context a dataset provides, the faster and easier it can be found and used by researchers.
 - Clear information on license conditions and access protocols ensures that researchers know under what conditions they can use the data. This saves tedious clarifications and administrative work. In addition, clearly defined access conditions are a prerequisite for ensuring that all legal and institutional requirements can be met.
 - Of course, one can ask whether it makes sense to describe every dataset so comprehensively, especially as the budgets and resources of the data producers are often limited. The following remarks apply:
 - You never know in advance for what purpose the dataset will be used in the future and you should therefore be generous when assigning metadata.
 - By consistently and continuously assigning detailed metadata, the data producer not only saves himself extra work later if he must laboriously reconstruct the context of the data again, but also for future users who want to use the dataset at a later date.
 - Comprehensive metadata prevents misunderstandings and can thus avoid or at least reduce the risk of a possible misinterpretation of the data by third parties.
 - In addition, as already mentioned, many questions from data consumers can be answered in advance by means of clearly documented and described datasets and unnecessary inquiries can be avoided.
 - Informative descriptions of the datasets are also a sign of quality and integrity, as the data producer demonstrates that it can describe the dataset in a transparent and comprehensible way, which in turn promotes trust in the data producer and the dataset itself.
- The reusability of the data records is considered from the outset when the data is created. Just as data protection is considered from the outset with data and applications («privacy by design»), the multiple use of data should also be planned for from the outset. Here are the reasons:
 - By taking reusability into account right from the design stage of the data collection, it is ensured that the data is structured, complete and well documented.
 - Reuse should also be in the interest of the data producers, as we have already read that there are many advantages to reusing the data.
 - Declarations of consent and data protection regulations are already considered during data collection to enable legal reuse.
 - Data that is intended for reuse from the outset is easier to integrate into other projects and analyses.
 - Standardized, widely used metadata schemas and data formats that can be used equally by humans and machine systems are used wherever possible. If these are

adapted and extended to the respective needs, this should always be done with a view to interoperability and reusability.

- Continuous version control and documentation of data changes support traceability and reuse. A complete data history makes it possible to understand the origin and development of the data and facilitates collaboration, as everyone involved works on the same basis and can track changes.
- An API is considered right from the start. APIs are essential tools for integrating data into different systems. They offer standardized, efficient and secure methods for data access and processing, which significantly improves the interoperability and reusability of data.
- A merger of existing and planned repositories should at least be examined. In the case of universities in particular, it should be examined whether it makes sense to create separate data collections for each individual university or whether these datasets could be stored from the outset in a shared, existing data repository such as SWISSUbase. This would bring the following opportunities, but also challenges:
 - Sharing infrastructure, personnel and technologies reduces costs and can increase efficiency immensely. This facilitates data exchange and increases integration between different systems and disciplines. It is easier to harmonize data sources than if there are several smaller, heterogeneous repositories.
 - However, education-specific metadata and requirements should not be neglected. Interfaces and functions may not be optimally tailored to the needs of education research.
 - Ensuring data quality and integrity in a larger, interdisciplinary repository is an additional challenge, but one that can be solved using appropriate quality control mechanisms such as validation systems.

Additional Considerations for Implementing FAIR Principles:

- Training for Implementing FAIR Principles:
 - Proper training is essential for the successful implementation of FAIR principles. Education institutions, data producers, and repositories need to invest in comprehensive training programs for their staff. These programs should cover the basics of FAIR principles, data management practices, and the use of relevant tools and technologies.
 - Ongoing training and workshops will ensure that staff stay up-to-date with the latest best practices and technological advancements. This continuous education approach will foster a culture of data stewardship and «FAIRness» within the organization.
- Resources (Finances, Time, Human) Needed for Implementation:
 - Implementing FAIR principles requires significant investment in terms of financial resources, time and staff. Institutions and data producers need to allocate sufficient budgets to support the development and maintenance of FAIR-compliant systems and infrastructure.
 - Securing funding for the necessary technological upgrades, staff training, and ongoing maintenance is crucial. Additionally, allocating dedicated time for staff to work on implementing and maintaining FAIR principles is essential to ensure sustained compliance and improvement.
- Rules and Guidelines from Authorities:
 - Establishing clear rules and guidelines from relevant authorities might provide a structured framework for the implementation of FAIR principles. These guidelines could outline the minimum requirements for metadata, data management practices, and interoperability standards.

- Authorities could also provide support and resources to help institutions and data producers meet these requirements. This could include funding opportunities, technical assistance, and access to shared infrastructure.
- Clear rules and guidelines will ensure consistency and uniformity in the implementation of FAIR principles across different institutions and repositories, ultimately enhancing the overall quality and usability of education data.

By addressing these additional considerations, the implementation of FAIR principles in education data repositories can be more effective and sustainable, leading to improved data quality, accessibility, and usability for researchers and other stakeholders.

Closing words

In conclusion, advancing the FAIRness of education data in Switzerland—ensuring it is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable—is a crucial step towards maximizing its value and utility. The FAIR principles provide a clear framework for improving how education data is managed and used, ultimately benefiting researchers, policymakers, and educators.

Currently, education data in Switzerland has a solid foundation, but there is significant potential for improvement. By focusing on making data easier to find and access, we can reduce the time researchers spend searching for information and increase the time they have for analysis and innovation. Enhanced findability and accessibility mean that valuable data is not lost or overlooked but can be effectively utilized to generate new insights and drive education advancements.

Interoperability and reusability are equally important. When data from different sources can be easily combined and reused, it opens new possibilities for research and collaboration. It ensures that data collected for one purpose can be repurposed for others, leading to more comprehensive and efficient studies. This approach not only maximizes the value of the data but also supports more sustainable and cost-effective research practices.

By committing to the FAIR principles, Switzerland can ensure that its education data is reliable, transparent, and useful. This commitment will foster a more collaborative research environment where data is shared and utilized to its fullest potential. Researchers will benefit from better access to high-quality data, leading to more robust and impactful findings. Policymakers will be able to make more informed decisions based on comprehensive and well-documented data. Educators will gain insights that can help improve teaching practices and education outcomes.

In summary, embracing the FAIR principles is a practical and above all a necessary step towards enhancing the utility of education data in Switzerland.

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Appendix:

1. *Glossary (in alphabetical order)*

- **Aggregated Data:** Data that has been compiled and summarized from individual-level records to provide a collective view. In the context of education, aggregated data is often used to present information on groups of students, schools, or education programs, enabling the analysis of trends and outcomes at a higher level without exposing individual data points.
- **Anonymization/Pseudonymization:** Techniques used to protect individual privacy in datasets. Anonymization involves removing or masking personal identifiers so that individuals cannot be identified, while pseudonymization replaces personal identifiers with pseudonyms, making it difficult but not impossible to re-identify individuals.
- **Authentication:** The process of verifying the identity of a user or system. In data management, authentication ensures that only authorized individuals can access sensitive data, enhancing security and preventing unauthorized access.
- **Data:** Raw, unprocessed information collected through observation or measurement. In the context of education, education data can refer to test scores, enrolment numbers, graduation rates, and more.
- **Database:** A structured collection of data that is stored and accessed electronically. In the context of education, databases are used to manage large volumes of education data, such as research data repositories. Databases are designed to ensure data integrity, security, and efficient retrieval and manipulation of data.
- **Data Documentation:** Comprehensive information describing a dataset, including methodology, data collection processes, and any data transformations. This documentation is crucial for understanding and accurately using education data. While metadata offers a summarised, technical overview, data documentation, often as an accompanying document, includes the broader context and instructions for data usage, ensuring accuracy and clarity in education research.
- **Data Encryption:** The process of converting data into a code to prevent unauthorized access. This is a critical security measure used to protect sensitive information in databases and during data transmission.
- **Data Linkage:** The process of combining information from different sources about the same entity, such as an individual, organization, or event. In the context of education, data linkage allows researchers and policymakers to create comprehensive datasets that provide a more complete picture of education processes and outcomes.
- **Data Portal:** An online platform that provides access to a collection of datasets. Data portals are designed to facilitate the discovery, access, and use of data by offering search tools, metadata, and often visualization capabilities. They are used by governments, research institutions, and organizations to make data publicly available.
- **Dataset:** A structured collection of related data points organized for analysis, often presented in tables or databases. In education, datasets may include information on student performance, school characteristics, and education outcomes.
- **Informed Consent:** The process by which a participant voluntarily confirms their willingness to participate in a study or project after having been informed of all aspects of the study that are relevant to their decision to participate. Informed consent ensures that participants understand the nature of the research, the procedures involved, potential risks, and benefits, and their rights, including the right to withdraw from the study at any time.
- **Metadata:** Data that provides information about other data, such as its origin, structure, and context. In education datasets, metadata might include details about how data was collected, the definitions of variables, and data collection dates. Metadata helps organize and locate the data efficiently.

- **Metadata Standards:** Established guidelines that define the structure, content, and format of metadata to ensure consistency, interoperability, and quality across different datasets and systems. In the context of education data, metadata standards facilitate the accurate description, sharing, and integration of data from diverse sources.
- **Open Data:** Data that is freely available to the public without restrictions. In education, open data promotes transparency and allows for widespread analysis and research on education systems and outcomes.
- **Open Research Data:** A subset of open data specifically related to academic research. It includes data that researchers share openly to facilitate replication and further study, contributing to scientific knowledge in education.
- **Privacy Preserving:** Methods and technologies used to ensure that individual privacy is maintained when collecting, storing, and sharing data. This includes techniques like data minimization, secure multi-party computation, and differential privacy
- **Repository:** A central place where data, documents, and other resources are stored and managed. In the context of education and research, repositories often refer to digital libraries or databases where research outputs, such as datasets, publications, and software, are archived and can be accessed by researchers and the public.
- **Research Data:** Data collected, observed, or created for the purpose of analysis to produce original research results.
- **Sensitive Data:** Data that requires protection due to its confidential nature. In education, this might include personally identifiable information (PII) about students or staff, which must be handled according to privacy laws and ethical guidelines.

2. Fictitious educational example data record

Title: Mathematics Performance of Students in Switzerland 2023

Creators:

- Dr. Anna Müller, University of Zurich, ORCID: 0000-0003-1234-5678, Email: anna.mueller@uzh.ch
- Prof. Dr. Max Mustermann, ETH Zurich, ORCID: 0000-0002-8765-4321, Email: max.mustermann@ethz.ch

Identifier: DOI: 10.1234/mathematics-performance-switzerland-2023

Description: This dataset contains the results of a nationwide survey on the mathematics performance of students in Switzerland in 2023. The data includes test results, demographic information, and education backgrounds of the participants. The survey aims to assess the impact of various educational factors on students' mathematics performance.

Publication date: January 15, 2024 (original publication date)

Version date: March 15, 2024 (date of this specific version, Version 1.2)

Topics:

- Education Assessment (ERIC Thesaurus)
- Mathematics Achievement (ERIC Thesaurus)
- Secondary School Students (ERIC Thesaurus)
- Standardized Tests (ERIC Thesaurus)

Keywords:

- curriculum standards
- learning outcomes
- student performance

Language: German

Publisher: University of Zurich, Contact: library@uzh.ch, GRID: grid.6500.0

Contributors:

- Maria Schmid, Research Associate, University of Zurich, ORCID: 0000-0001-2345-6789, Email: maria.schmid@uzh.ch

Related identifier(s):

- DOI: 10.5678/comparative-study-2022, Relationship: Preliminary Study

Funding:

- Swiss National Science Foundation, Grant Number: SNF-98765, Project Title: Education Research Switzerland

Methodology & Sampling:

- **Method type:** Quantitative

- **Instrument:** Standardized Mathematics Test
- **Data collection period:** March 1, 2023 to June 30, 2023
- **Population:** Secondary school students in Switzerland
- **Sample size:** 2000 students
- **Coverage:** Switzerland
- **Education level:** Secondary Level I
- **Age of students:** 12 to 15 years
- **Sampling method:** Random sample
- **Data collection protocol:** The survey was conducted in classrooms, with each student having 60 minutes to complete the test.
- **Data processing:** The data was anonymized and processed through a data cleaning protocol to ensure data quality.
- **Ethical considerations:** Consent from students and their parents was obtained before the study began. The Ethics Committee of the University of Zurich approved the study.
- **Data quality measures:** Pre-tests were conducted, and data collectors were trained. Inconsistencies in responses were corrected through follow-ups.
- **Additional Information:** Specific information on variables and attributes can be found in the data documentation ([Link](#)).

Data:

- **Format:** CSV, R
- **Size:** 50 MB
- **Version:** 1.2
- **File names:**
 - mathematics_performance_switzerland_2023.csv, 2.1 MB, 2024-03-15 / 03:40 AM (last update), md5:1d03c88f0fd707ee600b6ede4486e363 (integrity checksum)
 - mathematics_performance_switzerland_2023.R, 48.5 MB, 2024-03-15 03:42 AM (last update), md5:1d03c88f0fd707ee600b6ede4486e376 (integrity checksum)

Version history:

- **Version 1.0** (January 15, 2024): First release of the dataset with complete test results and demographic information of the students. (15. Januar 2024): Erstveröffentlichung des Datensatzes mit vollständigen Testergebnissen und demografischen Informationen der Schüler.
- **Version 1.1** (February 15, 2024): Minor corrections in the demographic data of the students and addition of metadata on the sampling methodology.

- **Version 1.2** (March 15, 2024): Update of anonymization procedures and provision of detailed documentation of data processing.
- More detailed change logs for each version are available under the following link, documenting all modifications and updates: <https://doi.org/10.1234/mathematics-performance-2023/changelog>

Access & registration/indexing:

- **Access rights:** Publicly accessible
- **Access conditions:** No restrictions, freely accessible to all users
- **License information:** Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0), <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>
- **The data set is registered and indexed in Zenodo:** <https://zenodo.org/record/1234567>
- **DOI:** <https://doi.org/10.1234/mathematics-performance-2023>

Interoperability Enhancements:

- Metadata in JSON: https://doi.org/10.1234/mathematics-performance-2023/metadata_json

3. Overview of FAIR Assessment education data sources in Switzerland

The following Tables 1-4 (see next pages) provide an overview of this FAIR Assessment, with Table 1 showing relevant international data repositories where data sets on Swiss education can be found, Table 2 national repositories or statistics portals, Table 3 institutional data sources of the universities, universities of applied sciences and universities of teacher education and Table 4 the statistics data portals of the cantons. Data sets from private providers that cannot be found or accessed publicly were not taken into further consideration.

The data source was assessed for each FAIR principle in the table. A green colour means that the respective FAIR principle is fulfilled, yellow means that the FAIR principle is partially fulfilled, and orange means that the FAIR principle is not fulfilled.

The «Remarks» column also contains any comments on access or the existence of a repository or other restrictions relating to the datasets.

Name of Datasource	Institution	Type of Data Repository	Coverage of Data	Number of Swiss Education Datasets	Typ of Data	Link to assessed education dataset	Remarks	F1: (Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier	F2: Data are described with rich metadata	F3: Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe	F4: (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource	A1: (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol	A1.1: The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable	A1.2: The protocol allows for an authentication and authorisation procedure, where necessary	A2: Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available	I1: (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.	I2: (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles	I3: (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data	R1: (Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes	R1.1: (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license	R1.2: (Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance	R1.3: (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards
Zenodo	CERN	Interdisciplinary	International	~ 7000	Raw data	https://zenodo.org/records/7063862		DOI	Metadata: - Title - Authors - Dataset description - Dataset content & preview - Identifier - Data type - Publication date - Publisher	Yes	Yes	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes	API xml, Metadata different formats (json, xml)	DataCite Metadata Schema, Dublin Core	Cross-reference to related study and other datasets	Sometimes data preview, but no further info about methods, sampling, etc.	Mostly open license, but when restricted, only contact email provided with no further details	Authors, publisher, and versioning, but info about data creators, collection, analysis.	No specific metadata for education needs Data in csv, xlsx
Figshare	Digital Science	Interdisciplinary	International	54	Raw data	https://figshare.com/articles/dataset/Data_for_Receptive_multilingualism_across_the_lifespan_PhD_thesis_/795286		URL	Metadata: - Title - Authors - Dataset description - Dataset content - Publication date - License - History	No	Yes, but hard to search by country	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, DataCite	API and Metadata xml	DataCite Metadata Schema, Dublin Core	No further references found	Only core metadata and some keywords, rights, file format & size, no further details about methods, sampling	Open license	Contact point, versioning, but no info about data creators, collection, analysis.	No specific metadata for education needs Data in different formats (csv, R, pdf)
Data Dryad	California Digital Library	Interdisciplinary	International	6	Raw data	https://datadryad.org/stash/dataset/doi:10.5061/dryad.5rk56gg		DOI	Metadata: - Title - Authors - Identifier - Dataset description - Usage notes - Location - Dataset content - Data type - Publication date - License - Keywords	Yes	Yes	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes	API json, Metadata xml, rdf	RDF, DataCite Metadata Schema, Dublin Core, OAI-ORE	No further references found	Core metadata and some keywords, rights, file format & size, some details about methods, sampling (but could be more)	Open license	Contact point, versioning, some details about collection, used tools	No specific metadata for education needs Data in very different formats (csv, docx, xlsx, pdf, ...)
Open Science Framework (OSF)	Center for Open Science	Interdisciplinary	International	Just 1 relevant dataset found about education in Switzerland	Raw data	https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/SE328		DOI	Metadata: - Description - Contributors - Resource information - Dataset content - Identifier - Publication date - Publisher - Keywords	Yes	Yes	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes	API json, Metadata xml	DataCite Metadata Schema, Dublin Core	Yes	Only core metadata and some keywords, rights, file format & size, no further details about methods, sampling	Open data license	Contacts, publisher, modified date, but no version history and other info about data creators, collection, analysis.	No specific metadata for education needs Data in different software-dependent formats (docx, xlsx)

Table 1: International repositories

Name of Datasource	Institution	Type of Data Repository	Coverage of Data	Number of Swiss Education Datasets	Typ of Data	Link to assessed education dataset	Remarks	F1: (Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier	F2: Data are described with rich metadata	F3: Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe	F4: (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource	A1: (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol	A1.1: The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable	A1.2: The protocol allows for an authentication and authorisation procedure, where necessary	A2: Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available	I1: (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.	I2: (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles	I3: (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data	R1: (Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes	R1.1: (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license	R1.2: (Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance	R1.3: (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards
SWISSUbase	FORS	Interdisciplinary	National	~ 225	Raw data	https://www.swissbase.ch/en/catalogue/studies/20227/ates/datasets/2469/2905/overview	-	DOI	Metadata in the corresponding study: - Study title in 4 languages - Authors - Institution(s) - Study period - Abstract - Geographical area - Funding - Method & Instruments - Population Metadata in the dataset: - Dataset title in 4 languages - Persistent identifier - Dataset description - Publication date - Versioning - Dataset content - Collection mode - Sampling info - Variables description - Usage license	Yes, but corresponding study has no identifier in the metadata	Yes	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes (DOI & Established Standards)	API xml, Metadata xml	DDI	The study displays all related datasets, but no other cross-references.	Sometimes the dataset has relevant education metadata, for example about the unit or population, but it is not consistent for all datasets.	Yes.	Yes, some datasets have detailed descriptions about provenance, but not consistent for all datasets.	DDI, but metadata are more oriented for social science (relevant education metadata not always provided) Data in different formats, sometimes software-independent formats (csv), sometimes software dependent formats (xlsx, exb, flk, strata)
opendata.swiss	Federal Statistical Office on behalf of the Federal Department of Home Affairs (FDHA)	Interdisciplinary	National	~ 1750	Raw and aggregated data	https://opendata.swiss/en/dataset/schulerprognose-base1	-	Internal identifier and URL, not clear if persistent.	Metadata: - Title - Organization - Dataset description - Dataset content - Identifier - Publication date - Publisher - Temporal and spatial coverage	Yes	Yes	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Not sure, internal identifier is provided	API json, Metadata xml	DCAT-AP CH	No further references found	Temporal and spatial coverage, but no further details about methods, scale, sampling, etc. External link to the source of the data could provide more info.	Open data license	Contact points URL, publisher, modified date, but no version history and other info about data creators, collection, analysis.	No specific metadata for education needs Data in a lot of different formats (xls, turtle, csv, json)
Federal Statistical Office	Federal Statistical Office	Interdisciplinary	National	~ 4500 tables (171 datacubes)	Aggregated data	https://www.pxweb.bfs.admin.ch/pxweb/de/px-x-1502040200_185/px-x-1502040200_185/px-x-1502040200_185.px	-	URL Datacube URL seems unique & persistent, table URL not clear if persistent.	General Metadata: - Title - Publication date - Publisher - Data type - Survey period - Internal Identifier (no info about creator, but contact) Additional metadata in datacube: - Identifier - Period - Geographical Area - Unit - Dataset content	Only in the datacubes	Yes, is searchable, but free text search only in titles.	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Not sure, internal identifier is provided	API json	Not info found about metadata standard	Sometimes, but not consistent	Datacubes have some relevant metadata about methods, tables not.	Only open aggregated data is available, info about access to raw data is there, but not easy to find	Only last update and few infos about method, but no versioning, history, details about data creation, collection and analysis.	Datacubes have some education metadata as education levels, but no standard Data in csv, xlsx, json (datacubes)

Table 2: National repositories

Name of Datasource	Institution	Type of Data Repository	Coverage of Data	Number of Swiss Education Datasets	Typ of Data	Link to assessed education dataset	Remarks	F1: (Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier	F2: Data are described with rich metadata	F3: Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe	F4: (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource	A1: (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol	A1.1: The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable	A1.2: The protocol allows for an authentication and authorisation procedure, where necessary	A2: Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available	I1: (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.	I2: (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles	I3: (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data	R1: (Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes	R1.1: (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license	R1.2: (Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance	R1.3: (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards
BORIS Portal	University of Bern	Interdisciplinary	Institutional	1	Raw data	https://boris-portal.unibe.ch/handle/20.500.12422/323	-	DOI	Metadata: - Title - Dataset description - Contact - Contributors - Identifier - Organization - Languages - Subjects & Keywords - Rights - Dataset content	Yes	Yes	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes	Metadata xml (Dublin Core)	Dublin Core	Cross-reference to collection, but not to other datasets found	Open license	Only contact point & organization, but no info about versioning, data creators, collection, analysis found	No specific metadata for education needs found Data in csv, txt	
yareta.ch	University of Geneva	Interdisciplinary	Institutional	19	Raw data	https://yareta.unige.ch/archives/48700998-c181-40fb-a0f4-d8feb5335b0	-	DOI	Metadata: - Title - Identifier - License - Contributors - Dataset description - Dataset content - Publication date - Publisher	Yes	Yes	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes	Metadata xml (DataCite)	DataCite Metadata Schema	Yes	Core metadata with other relevant metadata as sensitivity level, but could be more	Open license, when restricted, no info about data access found	Contact point, versioning, but no info about data creators, collection, analysis found	No specific metadata for education needs found Data mostly in pdf, docx, png, xlsx (not ideal for automated data extraction)
OLOs	University of Geneva, University of Applied Sciences Bern, Geneva School of Business Administration	Interdisciplinary	Institutional	36 (but only a few relevant for education needs)	Raw data	https://olos.swissportal/archives/031e385-6ef1-4092-988a-174175113188	-	DOI	Metadata: - Title - Authors - Dataset description - Dataset content - Identifier - Data type - Publication date - Publisher	Yes	Yes	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes	Metadata xml (DataCite)	DataCite Metadata Schema	Yes	Core metadata with other relevant metadata as sensitivity level, but could be more	Open license, when restricted, no info about data access found	Contact point, versioning, but no info about data creators, collection, analysis found	No specific metadata for education needs found Data mostly in csv, pdf and other formats
ETH Research Collection	ETH Zürich	Interdisciplinary	Institutional	unclear, datasets mostly not relevant to education researcher	Raw data	https://www.research-collection.ethz.ch/handle/20.500.11850/390053	-	DOI	Metadata: - Title - Creators - Publisher - Identifier - Dataset description - Dataset content - Data type - Publication date - License - Subject	Yes	Yes, but not enough filters to search for education data	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes	API and Metadata xml Data csv, xlsx, and other formats	DataCite Metadata Schema, Dublin Core	Yes	Core metadata and some keywords, rights, file format & size, but no further details about methods, sampling found	Open license	Contact point but no info about versioning, data creators, collection, analysis found	No specific metadata for education needs found Data in csv, R, txt, pdf
REPO PHBern	PH Bern	Interdisciplinary	Institutional	4	Raw data	https://phrepo.phbern.ch/6949/	-	DOI	Metadata: - Title - Authors - Publisher - Identifier - Associated Project - Dataset description - Dataset content - Data type - Publication date - Modified data - License	Yes	Yes	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes	Metadata xml	Dublin Core	References to project, but no references to related datasets found	Open license	Contact point, but no info about versioning, data creators, collection, analysis found	No specific metadata for education needs found Data in csv, pdf	
Academic Output Archive (ACQUA)	École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL)	-	-	-	-	-	Access restricted to EPFL researchers!	No public access to the repository	No public access to the repository	No public access to the repository	No public access to the repository	No public access to the repository	No public access to the repository	No public access to the repository	No public access to the repository	No public access to the repository	No public access to the repository	No public access to the repository	No public access to the repository	No public access to the repository	No public access to the repository	No public access to the repository
UNiverse	University of Basel	-	-	-	-	-	Access restricted to Uni Basel researchers!	No public access to the repository	No public access to the repository	No public access to the repository	No public access to the repository	No public access to the repository	No public access to the repository	No public access to the repository	No public access to the repository	No public access to the repository	No public access to the repository	No public access to the repository	No public access to the repository	No public access to the repository	No public access to the repository	No public access to the repository
-	University of Zürich	-	-	-	-	-	No institutional public data repository	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found
-	University of Fribourg	-	-	-	-	-	No institutional public data repository	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found
-	University of Lausanne	-	-	-	-	-	No institutional public data repository	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found
-	University of Lucerne	-	-	-	-	-	No institutional public data repository, only metadata available in institutional research database. Dataset are disseminated in ZENODO	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found
-	University of Neuchâtel	-	-	-	-	-	No institutional public data repository. Dataset are disseminated in SWISSUbase	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found
-	University of St. Gallen	-	-	-	-	-	No institutional public data repository	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found
-	University of Switzerland Italian USI	-	-	-	-	-	No institutional public data repository	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found
-	University of Applied Science in the Grisons	-	-	-	-	-	No institutional public data repository	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found
-	University of Applied Sciences and Arts Northwestern Switzerland (FHNW)	-	-	-	-	-	No institutional public data repository	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found

Name of Datasource	Institution	Type of Data Repository	Coverage of Data	Number of Swiss Education Datasets	Type of Data	Link to assessed education dataset	Remarks	F1: (Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier	F2: Data are described with rich metadata	F3: Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe	F4: (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource	A1: (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol	A1.1: The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable	A1.2: The protocol allows for an authentication and authorisation procedure, where necessary	A2: Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available	I1: (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.	I2: (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles	I3: (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data	R1: (Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes	R1.1: (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license	R1.2: (Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance	R1.3: (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards	
Dataportal Statistical Office Canton Aargau	Statistical Office Canton Aargau	Interdisciplinary	Cantonal	~ 40	Aggregated data	https://www.ag.ch/de/verwaltung/dfr/statistik/zahlen-und-vergleiche/datenauswahl-zweitbeBemoteUrl/datan/BN1STBN1TGN1T2M1		URL	Metadata: - Title - Description - Definitions - Source - Dataset Info - Publication date - Publisher - Variables	No	No	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Questionable, only URL	API & Metadata json	Not info found about metadata standard	Yes	Core metadata and some info about units, variables -> reference to statistical federal office	No	Contact point, but no info about versioning, collection methods, analysis found	No specific metadata for education needs found Data in csv	
	Statistical Office Canton Appenzell Ausserrhoden						No data portal, only website with some statistics	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found
Dataportal Statistical Office City of Berne	Statistical Office City of Berne	Interdisciplinary	Communal	20	Aggregated data	https://www.bern.ch/hemen/stadt-recht-und-politik/bern-in-zahlen/katost/15bilwis/15bilwis.xls		No separate URL for a specific dataset	Metadata: - Dataset title and content	No	No	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Questionable, no specific entry for the dataset found	No	No	Some corresponding download links, but no reference to further metadata found	No	No	Only contact point	No specific metadata for education needs Data only xls	
Dataportal Statistical Office Canton Berne	Statistical Office Canton Berne	Interdisciplinary	Cantonal	22	Aggregated data	https://www.fin.be.ch/de/start/themen/OeffentlicheStatistik/statistikportal/statistiksteckbrief.htm?searchParam_id=118		URL	Metadata: - Title - Source - Dataset Info - Publication date - Publisher - Collection and Analysis type - Some info about variables - Update date	No	Yes	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Questionable, only URL	Metadata not specified	Not info found about metadata standard	No further references found	Core metadata and some keywords, methods, population, variables	No	Contact point, some info about versioning and collection methods, analysis (but could be more)	No specific metadata for education needs Data mostly xls, pdf	
Dataportal Data and Statistics Office Basel Landschaft	Data and Statistics Office Basel Landschaft	Interdisciplinary	Cantonal	~ 45	Aggregated data	https://www.statistik.bl.ch/web_portal/15_1_1		URL	Metadata: - Title - Source - Update date	No	No	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Questionable, only URL	Metadata not specified	Not info found about metadata standard	No further references found	Not explicitly, but in attached pdf is additional metadata about method, population	No	Contact point, but no info about versioning in the attached pdf some info about collected variables found	No specific metadata for education needs Data only xls	
Dataportal Statistical Office Canton Basel City	Statistical Office Canton Basel City	Interdisciplinary	Cantonal	7	Aggregated data	https://data.bs.ch/explorate/dataset/100121/table/?disjunctive_schuljahr&disjunctive_perimeter&sort=schuljahr		Internal identifier and URL, not clear if persistent	Metadata: - Title - Themes - Publisher - Location - Dataset Info - Publication date	Internal identifier	Yes	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Not sure, internal identifier is provided	API json	DCAT-AP CH	Yes	Yes, details about population, sampling, education level, school year	Open license	Contact point, some info about versioning and collection methods, analysis (but could be more)	Yes, also metadata about education level, population, sampling No specific education metadata standard found Data in csv, json, xls	
Dataportal Statistical Office Canton Fribourg	Statistical Office Canton Fribourg	Interdisciplinary	Cantonal	3	Aggregated data	https://opendata.fr.ch/explore/dataset/15_02_elèves_lieu_ecole/table/?q=annee		Internal identifier and URL, not clear if persistent	Metadata: - Title - Themes - Publisher - Location - Dataset Info - Publication date	Internal identifier	Yes	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Not sure, internal identifier is provided	API json	DCAT-AP CH	Yes	Yes, details about population, sampling, education level, school year	Open license	Contact point, some info about versioning and collection methods, analysis (but could be more)	Yes, also metadata about education level, population, sampling No specific education metadata standard found Data in csv, json, xls	
Dataportal Statistical Office Canton Geneva	Statistical Office Canton Geneva	Interdisciplinary	Cantonal	~ 10	Aggregated data	https://statistique.ge.ch/domaines/15/15_03/tables/ta1		No separate URL for a specific dataset	Metadata: - Title - Publisher - Dataset Info - Publication date - Method	No	No	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Questionable, no specific entry for the dataset	No	No	Some corresponding download links, but no reference to further metadata found	Core metadata is lacking some info, but detailed info about method in general in a separate link found	No	Contact point, but no info about versioning in the separate link info about collection, variables found	Yes, also metadata about education level, sampling (only in html) No specific education metadata standard found Data xls	
	Government Office Canton Glarus						No data portal, only reference to the Federal Statistical Office	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found
Dataportal Office for Economy and Tourism Graubünden	Office for Economy and Tourism Graubünden	Interdisciplinary	Cantonal	3	Aggregated data		Only 3 xlsx files about education, all other data is in the BISTA database (Statistical Office Zurich City)	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found
Dataportal Statistical Office Canton Lucerne	Statistical Office Canton Lucerne	Interdisciplinary	Cantonal	~ 150	Aggregated data	https://www.lustat.ch/files_ftpdaten/ch/0000/w153_0051_ch0000_kt_d_0000_001_008_216.html		Internal identifier and URL, not clear if persistent.	Metadata: - Title - Internal Identifier - Publication date - Update date	No	Yes	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Not sure, internal identifier is provided	Metadata not specified	Not info found about metadata standard	No	Core metadata is lacking some info, but more info about method in general in a separate link found	No	Contact point, but no info about versioning in the separate link info about data sources and data collection, definitions found	Some metadata about education setting, sampling (only in html) No specific education metadata standard found Data xls	
Dataportal Statistical Office Canton Neuchâtel	Statistical Office Canton Neuchâtel	Interdisciplinary	Cantonal	13	Aggregated data		No education data in the data portal, but on the website are 13 xlsx files	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found
	Department of Economic Affairs Canton Nidwalden						No data portal, only reference to the Federal Statistical Office	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found
	Department of Economic Affairs Canton Obwalden						No data portal, only reference to the Federal Statistical Office	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found
Dataportal Department of Economic Affairs Canton of St. Gallen (stada2)	Department of Economic Affairs Canton St. Gallen	Interdisciplinary	Cantonal	109	Aggregated data	https://stada2.sg.ch/21a-b=indikatoren&jahr=0&indikatoren=374,278&gebiet=1&biestyp=1&gebiet=1		No separate URL for a specific dataset, but internal identifier	Metadata: - Title - Year of the data - In pop-up window: - Unit - Description - Source	Internal identifier	Yes	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Questionable, no specific entry for the dataset found	Metadata not specified	Not info found about metadata standard	Some corresponding download links, but no reference to further metadata found	Core metadata and some info about unit, but no further relevant metadata found	No	No	No specific metadata for education needs found Data xls	
Dataportal of the Coordination Office for Statistics Canton Schaffhausen	Economic Office of the Canton Schaffhausen	Interdisciplinary	Cantonal	3	Aggregated data	https://sh.ch/CMS/Websites/Kanton-Schaffhausen/Behorde/Verwaltung/Volkswirtschaftsdepartement/Wirtschaft-Statistik-und-Tourismus/Statistik-Portal-56749-DE.html		No separate URL for a specific dataset	Metadata: - Title - Source - Publication date	No	Yes	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Questionable, no specific entry for the dataset found	Metadata not specified	Not info found about metadata standard	No	No	No	No	No specific metadata for education needs found Data xls and pdf	
Statistical Portal Office of Finance Canton Solothurn	Office of Finance Canton Solothurn	Interdisciplinary	Cantonal				Only report "Schule in Zahlen" (pdf), all other data is referenced to the Federal Statistical Office	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found

Name of Datasource	Institution	Type of Data Repository	Coverage of Data	Number of Swiss Education Datasets	Type of Data	Link to assessed education dataset	Remarks	F1: (Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier	F2: Data are described with rich metadata	F3: Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe	F4: (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource	A1: (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol	A1.1: The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable	A1.2: The protocol allows for an authentication and authorisation procedure, where necessary	A2: Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available	I1: (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.	I2: (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles	I3: (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data	R1: (Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes	R1.1: (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license	R1.2: (Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance	R1.3: (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards	
Website of Office for Statistics Thurgau	Office for Statistics Thurgau	Interdisciplinary	Cantonal	~ 40	Aggregated data	https://pub.bista.tg.ch/de/zahlen-und-fakten/sdi/uebersicht-aller-personen-in-ausbildung/uebersicht/	Data is also published in the opendata.swiss Portal	URL	Metadata: - Title - Dataset preview - Data types	No	Yes	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Questionable, only URL	Metadata not specified	Not info found about metadata standard	No	No	No	No	No	No specific metadata for education needs found Data csv and xlsx
Website Office for Statistics of the Canton of Ticino Ustat	Office for Statistics of the Canton of Ticino Ustat	Interdisciplinary	Cantonal	~ 25	Aggregated data	https://www3.ti.ch/DFE/DR/USTAT/index.php?fu=section=temi.dati&p1=368&p2=1448&p3=1468&pr=old=145	-	No separate entry for a specific dataset	Metadata: - Title - Definitions	No	No	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Questionable, no specific entry for the dataset	Metadata not specified	Not info found about metadata standard	Some corresponding download links, but no reference to further metadata found	No	No	No	No	No specific metadata for education needs found Data xlsx
Dataportal Office for Statistics Canton Uri	Office for Statistics Canton Uri	Interdisciplinary	Cantonal	-	-	-	Only reports about education statistics (pdf), all other data is referenced to the Federal Statistical Office	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found	No public repository with relevant datasets found
Website Office for Statistics Canton Vaud	Office for Statistics Canton Vaud	Interdisciplinary	Cantonal	> 100	Aggregated data	https://www.vd.ch/etat-droit-finances/statistique/statistiques-par-domaine/15-education-et-sciences/enseignement-secondaire-ii#2070041	-	URL	Metadata: - Title - Source	No	No	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Questionable, only URL	Metadata not specified	Not info found about metadata standard	Some corresponding download links, but no reference to further metadata found	No	No	No	No	No specific metadata for education needs found Data xlsx
-	Department of Statistics and Fiscal Equalization Canton Valais	-	-	-	-	-	No data portal, only reference to the Federal Statistical Office	No public repository with relevant datasets	No public repository with relevant datasets	No public repository with relevant datasets	No public repository with relevant datasets	No public repository with relevant datasets	No public repository with relevant datasets	No public repository with relevant datasets	No public repository with relevant datasets	No public repository with relevant datasets	No public repository with relevant datasets	No public repository with relevant datasets	No public repository with relevant datasets	No public repository with relevant datasets	No public repository with relevant datasets	No public repository with relevant datasets	No public repository with relevant datasets found
Website Statistical Office Canton of Zug	Statistical Office Canton of Zug	Interdisciplinary	Cantonal	~20	Aggregated data	https://www.zg.ch/behoerden/gesundheitsdirektion/statistikfachstelle/themen/bildung/2-vollschule-und-privatschulen	-	No separate entry for a specific dataset	Metadata: - Title - Info about the statistic - Data type	No	Yes	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Questionable, no specific entry for the dataset	Metadata not specified	Not info found about metadata standard	Some corresponding download links, but no reference to further metadata found	No	No	No	No	No specific metadata for education needs found Data xlsx
Website Statistical Office City of Zurich	Statistical Office City of Zurich	Interdisciplinary	Communal	198	Aggregated data	https://www.stadt-zuerich.ch/pzd/de/index/statistik/themen/bildung-kultur-sport/bildung/bildungsst-and.html	-	No separate entry for a specific dataset	Metadata: - Title - Info about the statistic	No	Yes	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Questionable, no specific entry for the dataset	Metadata not specified	Not info found about metadata standard	Some corresponding download links, but no reference to further metadata found	No	No	No	No	No specific metadata for education needs found Data xlsx
Dataportal education statistics canton of zurich	Education statistics canton of zurich	Education	Cantonal	18	Aggregated data	https://pub.bista.zh.ch/de/zahlen-und-fakten/sdi/uebersicht-ueber-alle-lernenden/uebersicht/	Data is also published in the opendata.swiss Portal	URL	Metadata: - Title - Source - Dataset preview - Data types	No	Yes	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Questionable, only URL	Metadata not specified	Not info found about metadata standard	No	No	No	No	No	No specific metadata for education needs found Data csv and xlsx
Dataportal Statistical Office Canton Schwyz	Statistical Office Canton Schwyz	Interdisciplinary	Cantonal	14	Aggregated data	https://data.sz.ch/explore/dataset/lehrpersonens-tatistik/information/2disjunctive_schuljahr	-	URL	Metadata: - Title - Publisher - Keywords - Language - Dataset description - Dataset preview - Data types - Publication date - Geographical area - License	No	Yes	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Yes, HTTPS	Questionable, only URL	API json	Not info found about metadata standard	No, only to the administration	Core metadata and keywords, rights, file format & size, some information about method, but could be more	Open license	Contact point and some spare info about collection, but no versioning (only last update) or further info about analysis found	Metadata about education level No specific education metadata found Data in csv, json, xlsx	

Table 4: Cantonal data portals